

Building up slaveries in ancient Italy and the African savanna

© Walter Scheidel

Working paper, Stanford University, Version 1, September 2019

By the end of the Roman Republic, Italy had filled up with slaves: at least a million of them and probably more, even if not quite as many as once thought.¹ How had it come to that? For an answer, we cannot neglect the early formative stages of the Roman polity, the subject of this volume. But there we immediately encounter a forbidding dearth of evidence: whereas the steady flow of slaves into Italy during the last two centuries of the Republic is well attested, little is known about the “long fourth century.” Faced with this challenge, I adopt a somewhat unconventional approach. I begin with what is commonly thought of as being known but which, looked at more closely, can hardly count as being reliably established. I then sketch out different scenarios of what might have happened, put them into perspective by introducing a comparison that has not been employed before – with developments in sub-Saharan Africa up to the nineteenth century –, and finish by reflecting on what we may hope to gain from this exercise.

Italy

For a while, Moses Finley had given us a comforting if unreliable sense of the overall contours of change by envisioning a trajectory from more “archaic” forms of dependence toward fully-fledged chattel slavery. Early on (say, in the fifth and fourth centuries BCE), Roman bondsmen tied down by *nexum* or Etruscan “serfs” would have been more common than slaves. As political and military co-mobilization ushered in more civic rights, liberties and obligations, thoroughly “unfree” slaves came to be more starkly demarcated from “free” citizen-soldiers. Unshackled from personal dependencies, citizen armies proceeded to enslave their opponents across the Mediterranean and its hinterlands until – in Keith Hopkins’ deceptively elegant reconstruction – slave labor eventually undermined the livelihood of much of the citizenry: but that is another story.²

We know so little about social change in early Italy that this model may well be correct, if only by chance. Yet we must be wary. Finley promoted an analogous storyline for ancient Greece, which has begun to wither under the criticism of scholars who are chipping away at his claim that “intermediate statuses” (between slavery and freedom) once used to be the dominant form of personal bondage. As a result, the worlds of Homer and Hesiod have been repopulated with “proper” slaves and the status transition narrative has lost some of its luster.³ That alone ought to encourage us to rethink its Roman version as well.

This paper is based on my presentation for the conference “The Roman Republic in the Long Fourth Century” held at Princeton University, May 16-18, 2019.

¹ For a conjectural reconstruction and critique of earlier (higher) guesstimates, see Scheidel 2005: 64-71, with Scheidel 2011: 291-3.

² Finley 1980 83-89 = 1998: 151-7; 1999 66-9. On the free citizenry’s commitments (to war or other forms of mobilization) as a driver of slavery, see Scheidel 2008: 115-23, esp. 117-8 for Greece and Rome. Another story: Hopkins 1978: 1-74, esp. 30 (“Roman peasant soldiers were fighting for their own displacement”). This approach – essentially a variation on Appian, *Civil Wars* 1.7 – has not weathered particularly well: e.g., Launaro 2011: 168-77; De Ligt 2012: 162-5.

³ Greece: Finley 1980: 88-9 = 1998: 156-7; 1981: 156-66; 1999: 66-9. Harris 2012 and Lewis 2018: 89-92, 107-24 offer the most sustained critiques; see also Lenski 2018b: 125-8. Lewis forthcoming reviews local varieties of slavery across Greece that are often considered forms of serfdom. Finley’s use of the concept of “slave societies” (as opposed to “slave-owning” ones) is now at risk of ending up as a collateral casualty: e.g., Vlassopoulos 2016: 81-5, 95-7;

The most conventional approach is to look for references to slaves and slavery in fifth- and fourth-century BCE Italy. The canonical tally is modest but suggestive of deep roots. Thus, slavery appears well-established in the mid-fifth-century BCE Laws of the Twelve Tables. A tax on manumissions is reported – albeit several centuries later – for the year 357 BCE. The abolition of *nexum*, dated to 326 or 313 BCE, might conceivably have been facilitated by an expansion of slavery. The question of where to register freed slaves was said to have triggered discord in 312 BCE, which presupposes their presence in non-trivial numbers. The *lex Aquilia* of the 280s BCE specified damages to slaves. Moreover, accounts of enslavement of war captives go back to the regal period, all the way to the reign of King N° 5. The plot thickens later on, first with the alleged mass enslavement of the population of Veii in the 390s BCE and a century later with the Third Samnite War. Livy, our key source, supplies more and more precise numbers for the latter than he does for earlier campaigns, which – depending on how we count – add up to between 58,000 and 77,000 slaves taken over the course of just five years of warfare (297-93 BCE).⁴

What are we to make of this? Deep roots do not equate to large scale. More importantly, those reports that do hint at a sizeable slave presence tend to be less than compelling, as Karl-Wilhelm Welwei forcefully argued back in 2000.⁵ In the end, we will never know which – if any – of them to take seriously. At the same time, it would be rash to throw out the slave baby with the muddied bathwater of the annalistic tradition. If there is one thing about early Roman and Italian history that would seem hard to doubt, it is the ubiquity of armed conflict – and not just between the Romans and their endless line-up of enemies but also among Italy's inhabitants more generally.⁶ Unless pretty much everything we are told about the nature of these hostilities was made up later, these clashes generated lots of captives, who were liable to be turned into slaves. That later Romans were unsure about the origins of the term *sub corona vendere* – applied to captives sold into slaves off the battlefield – suggests that this practice was quite ancient indeed.⁷

Habitual enslavement of captives, however, did not necessarily translate to a dramatic expansion of slaveownership in Italy. Alternative means of disposing of captives were available. Ransoming was one of them. Common in classical Greece, where interstate warfare likewise yielded lots of human loot, this practice was – albeit once again much later – reported for Italy in the 290s BCE. But relatively low levels of monetization in Italy at the time cast doubt on the viability of such arrangements. For all we can tell, mass bailouts would have been harder to engineer than in much more monetized classical Greece. High-weight low-value *aes signatum* or *aes grave* would have been an inadequate medium for such transactions, even if Livy claims that it was used in staggering quantities.⁸

In this environment, export of captives might have been more a more attractive strategy. Hardly ever considered in modern scholarship – presumably because of the silence of the sources –, exports would allow us to reconcile the practice of large-scale enslavement in war with concerns about the ostensible dearth of employment opportunities for slaves or better (and especially archaeological) evidence for their presence. Conditions would have been favorable. Prior to the completion of the Roman takeover, peninsular Italy formed a readily accessible and exploitable periphery relative to wealthier core regions such as the Greek communities of Sicily and Southern Italy and the dominion of Carthage and its North African associates (centered on present-day Tunisia).⁹

Lenski 2018a: 39-46; but also Lewis 2018: 94-6 for a more nuanced view. Harper and Scheidel 2018: 103-5 defend this taxonomy. See also below at n.42.

⁴ References: Bradley 1985: 4-6; 2011: 242-5; and also Volkmann 1990: 36-40 for enslavement in early wars.

⁵ Welwei 2000: 23-42.

⁶ Even Terrenato 2019, who emphasizes the role of alliance-building and cooptation in Roman state formation, does not reject the tradition regarding endemic bellicosity.

⁷ Welwei 2000: 12-13.

⁸ Ransom was common cross-culturally, especially for elites: Patterson 1982: 107. For Greece, see Ducrey 1987: 19-23; Braund 2011: 117. Welwei 1995: 2-9 gives a gullible account of the ransoms reported for 295 and 293 BCE; but see Welwei 2000: 55-6.

⁹ Welwei 2000: 61 has been exceptional in even raising the possibility of exports; see also Scheidel 2012: 103. Exports would have gone in a long way in addressing the problem noted by Roselaar 2010: 73 that it would have been hard to

Analogous trade relations were well established in the eastern Mediterranean, where Greek poleis customarily imported slaves from peripheralized “slaving” zones in Thrace, the Black Sea basin, and western Asia Minor. Enslavement was generally undertaken by local parties who sold captives to Greek merchants.¹⁰ For the classical and Hellenistic periods, these transfers are clearly visible in epigraphic documentation from places such as Athens, Delphi and Rhodes. Unfortunately for our understanding of conditions in the Western Mediterranean, we lack analogous data from the western reaches of the Greek city-state culture. Tantalizingly, a handful of individuals from Italy are mentioned in the earliest manumission inscriptions from Delphi: reported in the early second century BCE, their presence presumably reflects the dislocations of the Hannibalic campaigns. Manumission decrees from Buthrotum, which faced Italy across the Strait of Otranto, likewise date from the second century BCE. We can only speculate that earlier and more western documents, if they existed, might show more slaves from Italy – a vexing case of absence of evidence not to be mistaken for evidence of absence.¹¹

By all accounts, the institution of slavery was entrenched among the western Greeks. Syracusan slavery is reasonably well attested, even if local “helots” loom large in the record, and mass enslavement of fellow Greeks was attributed to Dionysius I in the early fourth century BCE. During his raid of Pyrgi on the Etruscan coast in 384 BCE, he also took slaves who were then sold in Syracuse. It would have been quite remarkable if the Greeks of Sicily and Magna Graecia had not imported unfree persons from Italy on a more regular basis.¹²

A similar line of reasoning may be applied to Carthage. Recent work claims that Carthage was “awash in slaves.” Slaves hailed not only from the Berber frontier but also from various Mediterranean islands – Corsica and the Balearic islands –, and Greeks could be enslaved in Sicily.¹³ Italy would have been an obvious source of imports, and the Roman-Carthaginian treaties, which paid attention to coastal raiding, may indeed reflect relations of this kind.¹⁴

If one were inclined to step up conjecture, it would be tempting to speculate that the impact of Greek and Punic commercial capital might have intensified conflict in peripheral zones and directed it toward the enslavement of captives for export. Yvon Garlan has raised this possibility for the peripheries of the Greek Aegean in analogy to dynamics that are extremely well documented for early modern sub-Saharan Africa and may also have played out along the frontiers of the mature Roman empire. During the “long fourth century,” war-riven Italy would have been a prime candidate for such processes to unfold.¹⁵

These conjectures are informed by circumstantial evidence and an appreciation of context and analogy. According them a measure of respect would require us to be less enthralled by what the surviving – and generally much later – texts happen to claim and to be more open to probabilistic reasoning about what was likely to happen in a particular environment, even if it is not explicitly mentioned in what sadly passes for our evidence. After all, it would not be terribly surprising if Augustan-age writers had failed to be attracted to the image of the people of Italy being carried away into slavery, or if they had simply been unaware of such practices even if they had once existed. None of this calls for major leaps of faith.

Moreover, the export scenario would also make sense if – and I shall presently return to this “if” – we expect widespread slavery in Italy itself to have left a stronger mark on the material record. Commencing

sell large numbers of slaves during the early Republic “since at this time Rome did not have as much use for slaves as in later periods.” Cf. Bernard 2018a: 169 for slave trade *within* fourth- and third-century BCE Italy.

¹⁰ See now esp. Braund 2011: 120-3; Lewis 2018: 276-7.

¹¹ Lewis 2018: 278-80 discusses these datasets and their respective catchment areas, which could be quite limited. Except for the Hermokopidae auction texts from late fifth-century BCE Athens, these inscriptions date mostly from the third and second centuries BCE. Bresson 2019: 258-64 provides an exhaustive list of manumission texts from Illyria, Epirus and Akarnania: with few exceptions (mostly from Apollonia), they date from the second century BCE.

¹² Mass enslavement: Welwei 2000: 56-8. Helots: e.g., Carlà 2014.

¹³ Flaig 2009: 55-56; Lewis 2018: 259-66; Lenski 2018a: 26-9 (quote: 28).

¹⁴ Welwei 2000: 58.

¹⁵ Ducrey 1987: 25 (capital); Braund 2011: 123 (motivation for local enslavement); and now also Lewis 2018: 282-6 for the pull of Greek demand stirring up conflict elsewhere (in Thrace and Phrygia?). For the Roman empire, see below, n.17.

as it does around the mid-third century BCE, archaeological evidence of intensification of production and commerce (such as wine exports) appears only well after mass enslavement would already have been in full swing.¹⁶ This alone raises the possibility that even if lots of captives were turned into slaves, not all that many of them need have stayed put.¹⁷

Yet while that is certainly possible and might even seem plausible – which shows just how little we know for sure –, such a reading risks conflating two distinct matters: commercialized slavery – where owners paid for slaves with money and exploited them for profit – and more familial forms of bondage that did not necessarily coincide with economic intensification and would consequently be harder (or perhaps even impossible) to detect in the archaeological record. Roman-style slavery provided a suitable template for the latter: witness the formal emphasis on slaves being incorporated into the *familia* and the custom of manumitted slaves being associated with the owner’s lineage, a pattern that was common in other slave-owning societies in which slavery operated mainly at the household level and did not necessarily involve commercialized relations.¹⁸

This raises another and more heterodox possibility – that the very question of how or why slavery expanded in Roman Italy might be somewhat misconceived. What if slavery had already been common when the Romans set out to take over the peninsula? It is by no means out of the question that large numbers of slaves were already present at that time, pre-dating by far any subsequent commercialization and economic intensification. Greek sources make it appear that slaves were numerous in Thrace, in a familiar context of political fragmentation and endemic conflict. They even ascribe 300,000 (supposedly “helot-like”) slaves to the Illyrian Ardiaioi and 1,000 slaves or more to each of the two richest persons among the nearby Dardanians.¹⁹ Never mind what are bound to be fake numbers: what matters is that Greek observers seem to have found the notion of large-scale slaveownership among their non- or proto-state “barbarian” neighbors perfectly plausible. If just one of them had made a similar off-hand remark about early Italy, what would we make of it?

Tymon de Haas’s discussion of platform houses and population growth during the “long fourth century” suggests that at the very least there would have been room for widespread domestic slavery.²⁰ And as the *ager Romanus* grew, so would have employment opportunities for slaves.²¹ Absent large-scale market production, slave labor could have helped sustain unceasing warfare by freeing up adult male household members.²² The roots of Italian slavery may well have been both deeper and wider than we imagine. In this scenario, familial slaveholding on a broad scale would have coincided with and underpinned endemic warfare that was only later joined by growing commercialization. While the latter was likely to increase overall slave numbers – and in elite circles almost certainly did –, this expansion need not have been particularly dramatic or discontinuous. Discontinuities might have been confined in the first instance to the ends of slavery – to the ways in which slave labor was employed.

¹⁶ Thus most recently Bernard 2018b: 17-18.

¹⁷ Ideally one would want to see slave exports corroborated by (preferably ample) Greek coin finds: compare attempts to explain the distribution of Roman coin finds in Dacia with reference to the slave trade: Crawford 1977, with Stan 2014.

¹⁸ See Zeuske 2013: 156 (Rome), cf. 156-7 (Africa), and also generally 164, 168 for later intensification. See Saller 1994: 74-88 for the relationship between family, *familia* and *domus* in Roman discourse, and Mouritsen 2011: 37-40 for Roman freedmen as quasi-sons and 42-3 for *libertae suae* (one’s own manumitted female slaves) as respectable *concubinae* (consorts) and wives.

¹⁹ Lewis 2018: 100-101 provides references. Cf. Taylor 2001 for early indigenous slaveries, and Bresson 2019: 271-3 for the importance of slavery in northwestern Greece, adjacent to the Illyrian Balkans.

²⁰ In the conference volume.

²¹ Welwei 2000: 61-2; and see also Harris 1979: 59-60 and Scheidel 2012: 103. Roselaar 2010: 79 favors other options only because she remains wedded to the linkage between slave labor and marketized production.

²² Roman military mobilization rates were already high early on (from 346 BCE): Scheidel 2006: 220-3.

Sudan

This is not a completely fanciful outline: although it is not expressly supported by evidence for ancient Italy, it does reflect developments that took place elsewhere. By far the best examples come from sub-Saharan Africa, where slavery had been widespread well before major commercializing trends took hold. Enslavement was routinely used as a strategy to incorporate disempowered strangers into households and lineages in ways that allowed household heads to bypass conventional kinship structures and the constraints on exploitation these entailed. For centuries, sub-Saharan slaveries shared with their ancient Roman equivalent a feature that was relatively rare among societies characterized by large-scale slaveownership: the fact that capture in war and raids served as a principal source of slaves for the same group that undertook the warring and raiding.²³

In as much as it is appropriate to generalize, slavery in sub-Saharan Africa was grounded in domestic kin slavery that prioritized enslavement of women – who engaged in fieldwork and acted as sexual partners – as a means of attaching additional and subordinate women (alongside “honorable” wives) and their offspring to the elders in charge of households and lineages. Sexual relations and reproduction served as the most important means of gradual assimilation. These arrangements were not immutable: over time, one can perceive a grand arc away from kinship-based household settings and towards increasing institutionalization as slave labor assumed growing importance in the economy and slavery became *de facto* more detached from owners’ households – a shift that occurred in no small measure in response to the pull of international trade relations.²⁴

This outside influence had a long pedigree. Although the evidence for a trans-Saharan slave trade in antiquity remains scarce and often circumstantial, recent studies have made a plausible case for imports from Saharan and sub-Saharan areas into the Roman empire that provided infrastructure for later and better attested trade flows on a large scale.²⁵ Islamic influence made itself felt from the early Middle Ages onward, as societies of the Muslim “core” in the Middle East and North Africa region imported large numbers of slaves from sub-Saharan Africa (as well as from Europe and elsewhere). This in turn affected practices of slaveownership in Africa as well. Beginning with the Portuguese in the fifteenth century, the European (and transatlantic) slave trade built on and eventually greatly intensified these relations. Some local societies developed fully-fledged slave economies.²⁶

Similarly to the Red Sea and East African coast, the Sahel-Sudan zone became a principal frontier of Islamic intervention. From the seventh to the sixteenth century, somewhere around five million slaves were traded from the Sudan northward.²⁷ The Sudan, a savanna belt of tropical grassland with lightly wooded rolling but generally low-lying terrain characterized by wet and dry seasons that governed the rhythms of farming and transhumant pastoralism, turned into a belt of Muslim polities that reached from the Senegal River in the west to Lake Chad in the east. State formation critically depended on access to horses that enabled military power projection across the great plains of the northern savanna. In an institutionalized and self-sustaining cycle of violence and commerce, horses from farther north were exchanged for slaves from farther south, with the horses being used to capture more slaves.²⁸ But not all captives were traded away: others were put to work as laborers, soldiers and administrators, and – above all – women were kept as concubines. The build-up of a substantial servile workforce supported an early

²³ See Patterson 1982: 106-22 for a global view of capture in warfare and raids as a source of slaves. Lovejoy 2012: 22 notes the emphasis on direct enslavement, in contrast to practices in the Islamic Middle East and the colonial Americas. In the following, I provide a bare-bones outline of African conditions in recognition of the fact that this volume is aimed primarily at those who are more familiar with ancient Mediterranean history.

²⁴ Lovejoy 2012: 13-16 outlines the overall setting. Change over time: *ibid.* 18-19.

²⁵ Harper 2011: 86-91; Wilson 2012: 427, 432-5.

²⁶ Islamic influence: Lovejoy 2012: 15-18. For the role of commercial credit first from Muslim North Africa and then from Europe, see Miller 2012: 116.

²⁷ Lovejoy 2012: 24-26.

²⁸ Smaldone 1977: 9-12; Lovejoy 2012: 29-31.

plantation system in the Niger Valley (devoted to the production of staples such as millet, sorghum, wheat and rice) and the employment of slaves in gold mines and salt-works.²⁹

In terms of the retention of enslaved persons and the direction of slave exports, in the early modern period the Sudan stood apart from other African regions that became major suppliers of slaves to European traders. Its main counterpoint was West-Central Africa (Kongo and Angola) where the collapse of the Kingdom of Kongo (which had cooperated with Portuguese slave dealers) in the 1660s gave rise to warlordism and kinless warrior bands that replenished their ranks with enslaved boy-soldiers and exported other captives en masse. This region consequently came to account for the largest regional share of the transatlantic slave trade. Farther north, more successful state building both restricted and promoted exports, as emerging kingdoms such as Benin, Oyo and Asante shielded their subjects whilst converting populations along their frontiers into slaves.³⁰

In the savanna, the formation of the Songhay empire in the sixteenth century caused slave exports to the Islamic core regions to peak as raids ensnared ever more people. However, after Songhay succumbed to a Moroccan attack in 1591, the northern savanna came to lack large centralized states apart from Borno in the Lake Chad basin.³¹ The seventeenth and eighteenth centuries were characterized by endemic warfare: conflict over land and manpower – variously staged among Muslims, between Muslims and others, and as jihad against all – produced a steady stream of the newly enslaved. In what is now northern Nigeria, the five major Hausa states – Gobir, Zamfara, Kano, Katsina and Zazzau – fought dozens of wars while temporary hegemony passed between them and Borno strove to maintain some measure of nominal control over some of them. As before, slaves resulting from these conflicts were either retained or sold across the Sahara.³²

The slave trade was organized by Muslim commercial networks in which Hausa merchants (who were attached to individual city-states) played a major role. In long-standing circuits of exchange that were largely detached from the growing European-dominated Atlantic system, slaves were traded for cowries, iron bars, foreign silver coin, textiles and glass beads. The seventeenth and eighteenth centuries witnessed the formation of two distinct zones of slaving: the Islamic savanna belt with its consolidated holdings of slave labor, and areas closer to the coast where the pull of the Atlantic market transformed traditional kin-based slavery. Whereas the latter zone exported more slaves than it retained, the opposite appears to have been true in the savanna where demand for male slave labor was stronger. Political scaling-up in savanna polities such as Borno, Darfur and Futa Jallon allowed large slave estates to be set up.³³

In this environment, war, slaving and state formation were increasingly bound up with jihadist movements. From the late seventeenth century onward, a series of jihads sought to overcome warring states that were run by, and for the benefit of, narrow military elites whose predatory behavior prompted visions of a more unified and purified Islamic community.³⁴ Inspired by religious scholars, these movements had a strong ethnic component: Fulbe (Fulani), many of whom traversed the savanna as transhumant pastoralists, were almost invariably deeply involved in these campaigns.³⁵ The combination of pastoralist specialization, Islamic faith and a common language lent the Fulbe a distinctive identity that could be harnessed by its elites that controlled herds as well as landed estates and were well placed to organize larger operations. Structural tension between urban polities, such as the Hausa city-states, and Fulbe herders who were mobile and wary of taxation shored up the latter's capacity for collective action.³⁶

²⁹ Lovejoy 2012: 32-3.

³⁰ Kongo/Angola: Lovejoy 2012: 40-1, 76-80. State formation and exports: *ibid.* 46-67, 80-7.

³¹ For the fall of Songhay, see Gomez 2018: 315-67.

³² Lovejoy 2012: 68-74. Hausa wars and polycentrism: Smaldone 1977: 17. For Hausa city-state culture, see Griffeth 2000.

³³ Lovejoy 2012: 91-5 (networks), 107 (means of exchange), 112 (zones), 113 (population), 115 (uses), 117-8 (larger states).

³⁴ Lovejoy 2016 is the most comprehensive account; see esp. 37-8 for a list of major movements from the 1670s to the 1840s.

³⁵ I use the (anglicized) Fulfulde term Fulbe instead of the Hausa term Fulani.

³⁶ Smaldone 1977: 23; Lovejoy 2016: 45-6, 51, 58-9, 61.

In the Hausa region, endless warfare had forced many Muslims into slavery, a predicament that galvanized fundamentalists into action.³⁷ The most successful of them, the charismatic Fulbe scholar and imam Uthman dan Fodio, gathered followers to challenge the Hausa state of Gobir from within. In 1802 he declared the enslavement of fellow Muslims unlawful. Supported by Fulbe clan leaders and clerics, he launched open jihad two years later. Fomenting and exploiting local risings across a growing area, Uthman dan Fodio set up a franchise operation whereby he bestowed “flags” on other rebel leaders to legitimate their own operations.³⁸

During four years of intense conflict (1804-8), he and his followers managed to establish a caliphate in the central Hausa region: existing governments were overthrown and replaced by semi-autonomous emirs drawn from the Fulbe elite. The well-established kingdom of Borno farther east survived the caliphate’s assault in a diminished state. Further expansion targeted the south, where a rebellion of Ilorin slave soldiers in 1817 had brought down the Oyo kingdom. The empire – the Sokoto caliphate – that resulted from these campaigns was heavily segmented: effectively though not formally split since 1817 between Sokoto and Gwandu, it was made up of two central districts (centered on these twin capitals) and 33 emirates that in turn contained several hundred sub-emirates.³⁹

Officially, Uthman’s regime subscribed to a strict program of eliminating the social injustices attributed to previous governments, imposing full observance of Islamic rules, and preventing innovation that conflicted with such norms.⁴⁰ Slavery was a touchstone issue: followers of the caliphate were not supposed to enslave fellow Muslims but were permitted to fight fellow believers who failed to submit. The latter provision resulted in the capture and enslavement of huge numbers of Muslims. This conundrum, compounded by problems of rule enforcement, led to controversies about who counted as a proper “Muslim” and allegations of hypocrisy in treating members of the Islamic community.⁴¹

A movement that had been inspired at least in part by opposition to “illegitimate” enslavement thus brought about an unprecedented expansion and intensification of slave labor. The initial jihad destroyed major urban centers in the core region, which were sometimes replaced by new foundations. Turnover was at its most severe in the Sokoto and Gwandu areas: before long, the majority of the population (perhaps as many as four-fifths) of these centers came to consist of slaves who had been locally captured or forcibly relocated. Overall slave numbers across the empire were undoubtedly very large, even if we need to bear in mind that modern estimates are largely guesswork based on sporadic claims by contemporary observers and only imperfectly checked by European counts in the wake of the early twentieth-century colonial takeover. According to the current consensus, somewhere between a quarter and one half of the caliphate’s population was of servile status. Assuming a total of roughly ten million inhabitants, this guesstimate translates to several million slaves – at least as many as in nineteenth-century Brazil and possibly even as many as in the United States on the eve of the Civil War. Notwithstanding wide margins of error, we can be confident that throughout the nineteenth century, Sokoto was one of the largest slave societies in history.⁴²

³⁷ Lovejoy 2016: 62.

³⁸ For the jihad of Uthman dan Fodio, see Smaldone 1977: 19-37 and Lovejoy 2016: 68-101, esp. 68-9, 74-5, 80-3, 97.

³⁹ Prominence of the Fulbe in jihad: Lovejoy 2016: 93-8. Setup of the caliphate: Lovejoy 2005: 2-3, 230; 2016: 101, 109. The split was a result of an administrative division going back to Uthman’s reign: however, the subsequent rulers in charge of Sokoto and its dominion were the sole sultans whereas Gwandu was (merely) an emirate in charge of other, western emirates. Expansion to the south: Lovejoy 2012: 206-8.

⁴⁰ Lovejoy 2005: 156; 2016: 88, 99. This inspired later movements from the Mahdi in the eastern Sudan up to present-day Boko Haram (Lovejoy: 2016: 99-100).

⁴¹ Lovejoy 2005: 23-4; 2016: 92-3. Fugitive and rebel slaves played an important role as followers and allies of the emerging Sokoto system: Lovejoy 2005: 235-43.

⁴² Numbers: Lovejoy 2005: 1-3, 14, 231 (156 and 163, reproduced from much earlier articles, are outdated); 2012: 191-3, 202, 204; 2016: 102, 105-6, 109; Salau 2018: 52. Attrition at the core: Lovejoy 2005: 178-9. Settlements: Lovejoy 2016: 106-7. For the application of the concept of “slave society” to the Sokoto caliphate, see Lovejoy 2012: 21 (but cf. now 2018: 220-1); Lewis 2018: 97; Salau 2018: 19; and cf. also Lenski 2018: 32-4. See above, n.3.

Violent conflict is considered the principal source of slaves: the enslavement of opponents in the initial struggle to set up the caliphate as well as in later campaigns against rival polities and rebels; the takeover of existing slaves who had not joined pro-Sokoto risings; and far-reaching raids into non-Muslim areas. After the consolidation of much of the caliphate's territory in the early 1820s, routinized raiding – slave-catching expeditions – accounted for most of any new supplies.⁴³ While these operations ensnared numerous Muslims, injunctions against the export of co-religionists to non-believers appear to have been more faithfully observed. Consequently, with the exception of the well-established trans-Saharan trade, exports were curtailed, even if some victims of campaigning closer to the Atlantic coast did eventually end up in Brazil.⁴⁴

Sokoto's slave trade was therefore primarily a domestic affair, a mixture of commercial transactions, tributary transfers, and redistribution to followers. Much of this mobility was centripetal: every year, the subordinate emirates dispatched thousands of slaves as tribute to Sokoto and Gwandu.⁴⁵ Officials generally received land and slaves instead of salaries. Slaves worked both for this newly sedentarized and greatly enriched Fulbe elite and for wealthy Hausa merchants who had accommodated themselves to the new regime.⁴⁶ The sheer scale of empire boosted the scale of slaveownership at the top: dignitaries could own more than a thousand slaves each, often handed over to them as a reward for their services and loyalty, while individual Hausa investors managed to purchase dozens or hundreds. In what was a thoroughly hybrid system, redistribution served as the principal means of access to slave labor for the new state class of leaders and key associates whereas the civilian wealth elite relied on market transactions.⁴⁷

Slaves were forced into a variety of occupations. Traditional forms of employment as domestic servants and concubines remained of great significance but were complemented by large-scale commercialized production.⁴⁸ Textile production played a major role: the emirate of Kano was credited with 15,000 dye pits staffed by 50,000 slaves who manufactured goods for exports across the Sudan.⁴⁹ In addition, unprecedented numbers of slaves worked in agriculture: millet, sorghum, indigo, cotton and grain were the main crops.⁵⁰ In elite circles, farming was frequently organized within large estates that deserve the label "plantation" (at least when defined as "large scale-agriculture with slave labor, often organized in gangs," as Paul Lovejoy does), even if Sokoto society lacked a single specific term for these entities.⁵¹

On these estates, slave labor was centralized under overseers (free or slave) and slave drivers in charge of gangs, analogous to the mode of organization described by the Roman agronomists and widely practiced in the New World. Slaves were subject to direct supervision when they worked for their owners but were also expected to grow their own crops to complement their rations. Slave villages that enjoyed a greater degree of autonomy represented the main alternative form of organization. Fieldwork was concentrated in the rainy season whereas the dry season was given over to manufacturing, construction or textile production.⁵²

⁴³ Lovejoy 2012: 160, 204; Salau 2018: 91-4.

⁴⁴ Retention: Lovejoy 2005: 5, 20; 2016: 161 (and 133-66 on jihad and the slave trade in general). Trans-Saharan trade in the nineteenth century: Lovejoy 2005: 15. Drive toward the coast: *ibid.* 58. Brazil (Bahia): *ibid.* 55-80.

⁴⁵ Lovejoy 2005: 14, 171; 2012: 193, 203-4.

⁴⁶ Lovejoy 2005: 16, 171; 2012: 202; see also Salau 2018: 54 (land assignments), 124 (land and slaves in lieu of salaries). Slaves assigned to the elite from booty: Smaldone 1977: 92.

⁴⁷ Lovejoy 2012: 205; Salau 2018: 75-80. In addition, merchants could join campaigns and share booty, or engage in kidnapping: Salau 2018: 53.

⁴⁸ Concubinage: Lovejoy 2005: 117-52. Other sectors: *ibid.* 15-16, and see below. Stilwell 2000 discusses the status of royal slaves.

⁴⁹ Kano: Lovejoy 2005: 183; 2012: 203. For the textile sector, see Lovejoy 2016: 127-32.

⁵⁰ Crops and regional variation in production: Lovejoy 2005: 163, 168, 173-5; Salau 2018: 84. For the development of Kano and its concentration of textile (export) industries, see Salau 2018: 70-3.

⁵¹ Salau 2018 is now the most comprehensive study. Expansion of plantation economy: Lovejoy 2005: 176-99; 2012: 203; Salau 2018: 61-73; also in general Lovejoy 2016: 110-27. Plantation sector: Lovejoy 2005: 153-206 (definition [quote]: 154, no term: 161). Salau 2018: 24-9, esp. 27-8, argues for the applicability of the concept of "plantation."

⁵² Organization of the plantation sector: Lovejoy 2005: 165-7; 2012: 212-6; Salau 2018: 74-89.

Much of the output was used to support palaces and elite retinues as well as military forces. The central emirates shipped grain and cotton for consumption and processing to commercial centers such as Kano, which required more than they produced.⁵³ Goods were also sold in local markets. The plantation system thus sustained both domestic consumption and transregional commerce.⁵⁴

Overall, mass slavery was fundamental to Sokoto's political economy. The ruling class recruited slaves by means of routinized organized violence and employed them to preserve its social power with the help of the massive economic benefits derived from their accumulation, exploitation and sale. Enslavement of captives had become institutionalized via war and raiding – what Jack Goody called the “means of destruction” –, tributary allocation and redistribution, and market exchange. Unlike in other parts of sub-Saharan Africa, the demands of the regional economy trumped the pull of the Atlantic export trade. This was true both with regard to the transfer of slaves and to the so-called “legitimate trade” that had local slaves produce commodities for long-distance export to Western societies that had formally turned away from slave labor or the slave trade. This latter type of commerce was once again much more common along the coasts than in the Sudan. As Lovejoy poignantly observes, the greatest concentration of slaves in nineteenth-century Africa thus coincided with the weakest articulation between slavery and commercial capitalism.⁵⁵

Comparisons

Separated by 2,000 miles and 2,000 years, the Roman Republic and the Sokoto caliphate nevertheless had much in common.⁵⁶ This was true despite significant ecological differences that motivated societies to prioritize access to land in Italy and to manpower in the Sudan.⁵⁷ In both cases, war yielded masses of slaves. To be sure, motivations for warfare varied. Yet although the Romans are not known to have waged jihad, the religious drive behind their initial aggression must not be underrated and may well have been more crucial than later secularized accounts reveal: during the fourth and third centuries BCE, their wars paid for an awful lot of temples.⁵⁸ Conversely, religious devotion in Sokoto clearly had its limits, as fellow Muslims were routinely captured and enslaved for material gain.

Most importantly, war was a steady state: annual levies to raise forces for raids and punitive expeditions were as common in Rome as they were in the caliphate. In both cases, warfare acted as a vital means of coercive redistribution, of land as well as labor. Martial prowess was a crucial criterion for elite advancement, required to obtain titled office, whether as a Roman senior magistrate or a Sokoto emir. “War, booty, and political dominance constituted mutually reinforcing elements” not merely for the caliphate's ruling class but just as clearly for Rome's senators and knights.⁵⁹

Military styles differed in keeping with ecological differences, which lent greater importance to cavalry in the Sudan. Even so, during the caliphate's formative phase, Sokoto warfare bore some resemblance to Roman traditions by being relatively (that is, by local standards) egalitarian in nature. According to the classic modern account, it displayed “distinctive features of the raiding citizen army,” a notion that is readily applicable to the early Roman legions too: it was only later in the nineteenth century

⁵³ Lovejoy 2012: 214, 277.

⁵⁴ Lovejoy 2005: 169-73; Salau 2018: 129.

⁵⁵ Institutionalization: Lovejoy 2012: 278. Regional vs. export economies, slave numbers and capitalism: *ibid.* 285. On the “legitimate trade” in general, see *ibid.* 141, 165-90.

⁵⁶ These similarities make it all the more surprising that comparisons have so far been almost non-existent: for very brief observations, see Scheidel 2011: 96; Lenski 2018a: 34. In the following, I largely limit references to the African side of the comparison (cf. above, n.23).

⁵⁷ Salau 2018: 98. The latter was qualified by increasing demand for land due to nineteenth-century population growth.

⁵⁸ Rüpke 1990; Padilla Peralta 2020.

⁵⁹ Smaldone 1977: 58, 93, 139, 141, 149 (quote); see also Salau 2018: 128.

that growing social differentiation favored elite cavalry and their retainers, just as Roman warfare became less democratic over time, albeit much more slowly and far less starkly so.⁶⁰

In terms of political organization, both imperial powers are best described as complex conglomerates, made up of hundreds of *municipia*, *coloniae* and allied polities in Italy and of hundreds of subemirates in the caliphate. Both of them invested in networks of fortified settlements, colonies in Italy and ribats in the Sudan. Direct governance was effectively confined to the central regions, to Rome and its hinterland (where residents could routinely participate in the business of politics and ritual and public goods were dispensed) and to the twin capital districts of Sokoto and Gwandu. In both cases, the political centers and the economically most vibrant areas were not the same: witness the relative commercial importance of Campania and Kano.⁶¹

The two societies resembled each other even more closely with respect to slavery. Slaveholding had originally been embedded in familial relations. In both cases we encounter the notion of inherently “free” persons who could not legitimately be enslaved, Roman citizens and ethnic Fulbe.⁶² At the same time, slavery was not racialized: everyone outside the core groups was fair game, including, de facto, fellow Muslims. Assimilation persisted in the face of the violent acquisition of slaves and intensifying exploitation at arm’s length: slave women in the Sudan and Roman freedpersons who assumed elements of their patrons’ names are the most notable examples.⁶³ Slaves were present across so many different sectors that they did not form a distinct class. And unlike in many other large-scale slave systems outside the New World, slave labor played a prominent role in agriculture.⁶⁴

More trivial parallels merit only passing notice. These include slaves gaining permission to work on their own account (what the Romans called *peculium*) in exchange for payments to their owners, which in Sokoto were known as *murgu* (if paid in cash or cowries) and *wuri* (if delivered as a share of income), and slaves’ associated opportunity to save funds with an eye to purchasing their own freedom (in a process known as *fansa* in Sokoto). Manumitted slaves became clients. First-generation slaves (*bayi* in Sokoto) were distinguished from (more highly regarded) home-born slaves (*vernae* in Rome, *cucanawa* in Sokoto). Field hands were conceptually differentiated from domestics. General overseers (such as *procuratores*) would monitor estate managers (*vilici*), who were generally slaves.⁶⁵

Moreover, the African experience sometimes offers suggestions on issues for which we lack specific information regarding early Rome. For example, in the Sudan slave exports played a greater role prior to the formation of the Sokoto empire. This might make us wonder whether this had also been true of Italy prior to the Roman takeover: sub-Saharan Africa provides a real-life example of my earlier conjecture along these lines. Upon imperial consolidation, most slaves were retained within the respective conquest states.

Market mechanisms for the transfer of slaves existed in both societies. Yet the considerable significance of non-market redistribution in the caliphate raises the question whether similar processes also

⁶⁰ Smaldone 1977: 129 (quote). The intensity of warfare peaked from 1804 to 1837, then abated (ibid. 157), a process that coincided with disequalizing organizational changes (ibid. 129-33).

⁶¹ Conglomerates: Lovejoy 2005: 15. Ribats: Smaldone 1977: 61; Lovejoy 2005: 180; 2016: 97; Salau 2018: 51-4.

⁶² Lovejoy 2005: 22. But in general enslavability was determined by religious affiliation rather than race or ethnicity: Salau 2018: 31-46, esp. 45.

⁶³ Assimilation under Sokoto: Lovejoy 2012: 220-4, who mentions manumission via death-bed grants, self purchasing, ransom and favors to concubines with children (223), all of which have Roman parallels; likewise the fact that most slaves were not thus privileged (224).

⁶⁴ Farming, not a class: e.g., Lovejoy 2005: 16-17. Hausa partible inheritance laws fueled the need for ongoing raids to replenish fragmenting domains (Smaldone 1977: 148; also Salau 2018: 98): a similar mechanism might be hypothesized for Roman society.

⁶⁵ Lovejoy 2005: 44, 207-26 9 (*murgu*), 210 (*wuri*, a tithe), 43, 209 (*fansa*); Salau 2018: 102 (*cucanawa*), 85 (rural vs domestic), 81 (levels of hierarchy). Cato, *On Agriculture* 59 (one new piece of clothing to be issued to farm slaves every other year) was even stingier than some Sokoto owners: Lovejoy 2012: 213 (once per year). Treatment of slaves in Sokoto could be severe, once again mirroring Roman practices: Lovejoy 2005: 247; 2012: 215-6. Slave revolts were rare: Salau 2018: 112.

occurred during Italy's "long fourth century." The Sokoto elite was allocated slaves outright (alongside land grants): emirs and lesser officials received the most generous shares and were free to keep these slaves, pass them on to their retainers, or sell them off.⁶⁶ Under the Roman system of aristocratic oligarchy, commanding officers enjoyed great discretion regarding the distribution of war booty. In principle, there was little to prevent them from keeping some captives for their own use and that of their peers who accompanied them on campaigns, or from distributing them to their soldiers. A few accounts of doubtful reliability hint at such practices: just as the caliphate's soldiers expected booty to be shared on the battlefield, similar conventions may have applied among Romans. References to Roman soldiers receiving slaves not only reach back to the campaigns of Coriolanus and the sack of Fidenae in 425 BCE but also, and comfortingly for those skeptical of such semi-mythical tales, still show up in Caesar's account of his campaigns in Gaul in the 50s BCE.⁶⁷

We have to allow for the possibility that the redistribution of captives taken in military operations played a greater role in the early stages of Roman state building than the sources indicate. This conjecture would make it easier to reconcile references to mass enslavement with low levels of monetization and commercialization. It shows how slaveholdings great and small could have been built up without cash changing hands, enabling farmer-soldiers to take home one or two extra workers and aristocrats to grab many more. Absent the need to recover initial investments, such slaves could have been employed to sustain households at various status levels, by contributing to elite ostentation and largess and by freeing up commoners for continuous warmaking.⁶⁸ Such arrangements, elements of which are well attested for the Sokoto empire, would also have been perfectly consistent with Roman needs and mores. We might even ask whether the Sokoto practice of using slaves as a means of payment for larger transactions might have been anticipated in cash-poor Italy.⁶⁹

In sub-Saharan Africa, the employment of slave labor for the manufacturing of export goods was a late feature, motivated in the first instance by British measures against the international slave trade. Even then, the massive scale of Sokoto's domestic market held down investment in this sector. This serves as a reminder that production of goods for export is not a logical corollary of mass slavery. Thus, at the very least, there is no need to interpret the commencement of such exports in mid-third century BCE Italy as indicative of the relative insignificance or small scale of slavery in previous generations. Likewise, access to cash was not a necessary precondition for slaveownership on a large scale: the use of cowrie shells, iron bars and foreign silver coins to arrange transfers for many of the millions of slaves kept in the caliphate leaves ample room for us to imagine a substantial slave trade within Italy conducted with the help of basic bronze monies and imported Greek coins.

In practical terms, the main value of this type of conjectural reasoning by analogy lies in the fact that it provides food for thought. My very brief comparison between early Rome and the Sudan up to the Sokoto caliphate is meant to draw our attention to features that are given short shrift or not mentioned at all in the existing record for Italy in the "long fourth century." One of them is the fact that conditions in the western Mediterranean at the time would have favored the export of war captives from the Italian peninsula. The allocation of such captives to war leaders and soldiers in the wake of military operations is another. In the Sokoto caliphate, both land and people were forcibly appropriated and redistributed. Roman sources routinely refer to the seizure and transfer of enemy territory but show far less interest in the assignment of war captives. Instead we are treated to tales of ransom or local sale that may well be anachronistic in that

⁶⁶ Lovejoy 2005: 163, 171-3, 232.

⁶⁷ Sokoto: Smaldone 1977: 91-2. Rome: Volkmann 1990: 37 (fifth century BCE), 52, 147 (Caesar). Although Welwei 2000: 25 expresses doubts about the Fidenae allocations, reportedly limited to officers and cavalymen (Livy 4.34.4), he deems this practice plausible for the period of the Samnite Wars (156).

⁶⁸ As I speculated in Scheidel 2012: 103, "[i]n a period of little regular state income and primitive accumulation through plunder, slaveownership represented one of the few opportunities for elites to privatize the gains from empire." I note in passing that I am far less impressed than James Tan (in the conference volume) by early *tributum*: the very few references to the relevant rates imply a very low tax on income.

⁶⁹ Smaldone 1977: 148.

they are more readily compatible with – and thus perhaps influenced by – the customs of a later, more cash-rich age. It should give us pause that ostensibly plausible means of disposing of captives are not mentioned at all or not enough while less credible ones receive more attention. A comparative perspective deepens such concerns.

The Sokoto experience demonstrates that it was perfectly feasible to establish slavery on a large scale in the absence of widespread intensification of productive activities and a developed export trade for slave-made goods. The more slavery was fueled by capture in war waged by slaveowners and their subordinates, the less it would have depended on commercial incentives. This was true of early Rome and the Sudan but far less so of better-known slave societies such as classical Greece – where domestic captives were often ransomed and actual slaves were primarily imported from less monetized and commercialized regions –, and not at all of the colonial plantation systems of the Americas, where commercial capital was king and the creation of slaves was effectively outsourced to business partners on a different continent.

To be sure, analogies are not history, and possibilities or probabilities are not what actually happened. Evidence for one case cannot and must not be used to fill gaps in the evidence for another. That is not the point of comparison.⁷⁰ In the present context, comparison helps us transcend the biases of the existing record; alerts us to plausible options – made plausible by the simple fact that they reflect actual outcomes elsewhere and are not merely the product of our imagination –; and makes us think harder about these biases and options as we go about our business. Whilst fraught with its own set of pitfalls and temptations, this approach seems preferable to the conventional game of re-shuffling and massaging the same factoids over and over again, a frustrating pursuit that has kept students of the literary record of early Roman history busy for many generations without yielding much of substance – in marked contrast to archaeological research.

But there is more to this particular comparison. While comparative perspectives have gained ground in the study of Greek and Roman slavery, they have been dominated by references to the well-researched slave societies of the New World – and above all to the United States, even if practices of slavery in Brazil and other parts of Latin America may have had more in common with their Roman antecedents.⁷¹ This is hardly surprising given the sheer amount and accessibility of pertinent scholarship, and is without any doubt worth developing in much greater depth. That said, this orientation toward colonial or colonial-origin slavery reinforces Eurocentric notions of what matters most, sidelining alternative sources of inspiration and reflection.

Sub-Saharan Africa was not merely a source of slave labor for Western plantation owners, it also housed major slave societies that followed their own developmental dynamics. In the Sudan, the institution of slavery evolved at some remove from the pull of Western markets, in closer interaction with the slave-owning Islamic societies of the Middle East and North Africa region – not coincidentally yet another much-neglected candidate for fruitful comparison – and, in the nineteenth century, expanded in response to domestic concentration of power. Embedded as they are in disciplinary traditions that have long prioritized European or Western experiences in terms of approach as well as content, historians of the Roman world stand to gain from opening up to African history. The intellectual case for comparative engagement is strong. So is the moral one.

⁷⁰ For the uses and different flavors of comparative history, see the survey by Lange 2013, and more narrowly Scheidel 2018, directed at ancient historians.

⁷¹ Lenski's 2018b: 129-45 critique of Finley's lumping together Athens, Rome and the Antebellum South targets merely the tip of the iceberg; comparison benefits from the widest possible scope. Bradley 1994, with his emphasis on slavery in Brazil rather than the United States as a comparandum to Roman slavery, made a step in the right direction, but much more remains to be done.

References

- Bernard, Seth. 2018a. *Building mid-Republican Rome: labor, architecture, and the urban economy*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Bernard, Seth. 2018b. "The social history of early Roman coinage." *Journal of Roman Studies* 108: 1-26.
- Bradley, Keith. 1985. "The early development of slavery at Rome." *Historical Reflections / Réflexions Historiques* 12: 1-8.
- Bradley, Keith. 1994. *Slavery and society at Rome*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bradley, Keith. 2011. "Slavery in the Roman republic." In Bradley and Cartledge, eds. 2011: 241-264.
- Bradley, Keith and Cartledge, Paul, eds. 2011. *The Cambridge world history of slavery. Volume I: the ancient Mediterranean world*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Braund, David. 2011. "The slave supply in classical Greece." In Bradley and Cartledge, eds. 2011: 112-133.
- Bresson, Alain. 2019. "Slaves, fairs and fears: Western Greek sanctuaries as hubs of social interaction." In Freitag, Klaus and Haake, Matthias, eds. *Griechische Heiligtümer als Handlungsorte: zur Multifunktionalität supralokaler Heiligtümer von der frühen Archaik bis in die römische Kaiserzeit*. Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag: 251-277.
- Carlà, Filippo. 2014. "Ein Sklavenaufstand in Syrakus (414 v. Chr.)." *Incidenza dell'antico: dialoghi di storia greca* 12: 61-89.
- Crawford, Michael H. 1977. "Republican denarii in Romania: the suppression of piracy and the slave-trade." *Journal of Roman Studies* 67: 117-124.
- De Ligt, Luuk. 2012. *Peasants, citizens and soldiers: studies in the demographic history of Roman Italy 225 BC – AD 100*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Finley, Moses I. 1980. *Ancient slavery and modern ideology*. London: Chatto and Windus.
- Finley, Moses I. 1981. *Economy and society in ancient Greece*. Ed. Brent D. Shaw and Richard P. Saller. London: Chatto and Windus.
- Finley, Moses I. 1998. *Ancient slavery and modern ideology*. Expanded ed. by Brent D. Shaw. Princeton: Markus Wiener.
- Finley, Moses I. 1999. *The ancient economy*. Updated ed. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Flaig, Egon. 2009. *Weltgeschichte der Sklaverei*. Munich: C. H. Beck.
- Garlan, Yvon. 1987. "War, piracy and slavery in the Greek world." In Moses I. Finley, ed., *Classical slavery*. London: Frank Cass: 9-27.
- Gomez, Michael A. 2018. *African dominion: a new history of empire in early and medieval West Africa*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Griffeth, Robert. 2000. "The Hausa city-states from 1450 to 1804." In Mogens H. Hansen, ed., *A comparative study of thirty city-state cultures: an investigation conducted by the Copenhagen Polis Centre*. Copenhagen: The Royal Danish Academy of Sciences and Letters: 482-506.
- Harper, Kyle. 2011. *Slavery in the late Roman world, AD 275–425*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Harper, Kyle and Scheidel, Walter. 2018. "Roman slavery and the idea of "slave society." In Lenski and Cameron, eds. 2018: 86-105.
- Harris, Edward M. 2012. "Homer, Hesiod, and the "origins" of Greek slavery." *Revue des Etudes Anciennes* 114: 345-366.
- Harris, William V. 1979. *War and imperialism in Republican Rome, 327-70 BC*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hopkins, Keith. 1978. *Conquerors and slaves: sociological studies in Roman history, vol. 1*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lange, Matthew. 2013. *Comparative-historical methods*. Los Angeles: Russell Sage Foundation.
- Launaro, Alessandro. 2011. *Peasants and slaves: the rural population of Roman Italy (200 BC to AD 100)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lenski, Noel. 2018a. "What is a slave society?" In Lenski and Cameron, eds. 2018: 15-57.

- Lenski, Noel. 2018b. "Ancient slaveries and modern ideology." In Lenski and Cameron, eds. 2018: 106-147.
- Lenski, Noel and Cameron, Catherine M., eds. 2018. *What is a slave society? The practice of slavery in global perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lewis, David M. 2018. *Greek slave systems in their eastern Mediterranean context, c.800-146 BC*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lewis, David. M. Forthcoming. "The local slave systems of ancient Greece."
- Lovejoy, Paul E. 2005. *Slavery, commerce and production in the Sokoto Caliphate of West Africa*. Trenton: Africa World Press.
- Lovejoy, Paul E. 2012. *Transformations in slavery: a history of slavery in Africa*. 3rd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lovejoy, Paul E. 2016. *Jihad in West Africa during the age of revolutions*. Athens OH: Ohio University Press.
- Lovejoy, Paul E. 2018. "Slavery in societies on the frontiers of centralized states in West Africa." In Lenski and Cameron, eds. 2018: 220-247.
- Miller, Joseph C. 2012. *The problem of slavery as history: a global approach*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Mouritsen, Henrik. 2011. *The freedman in the Roman world*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Padilla Peralta, Dan-el. 2020. *Divine institutions*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Patterson, Orlando. 1982. *Slavery and social death: a comparative study*. Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press.
- Prachner, Gottfried. 1995. "Untersuchungen zum Verhältnis von Lösegeld-Forderungen für Kriegsgefangene im 4. und 3. Jahrhundert v.Chr., zu den Verkaufserlösen bei einer Auktion im Jahre 293 v.Chr. und Sklavenpreisen im italisch-sizilischen und griechischen Raum sowie in Ägypten." *Laverna* 6: 1-40.
- Roselaar, Saskia T. 2010. *Public land in the Roman republic: a social and economic history of ager publicus in Italy, 396-89 BC*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Rüpke, Jörg. 1990. *Domi militia: die religiöse Konstruktion des Krieges in Rom*. Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag.
- Salau, Mohammad Bashir. 2018. *Plantation slavery in the Sokoto caliphate: a historical and comparative study*. Rochester: University of Rochester Press.
- Saller, Richard P. 1994. *Patriarchy, property and death in the Roman family*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Scheidel, Walter. 2005. "Human mobility in Roman Italy, II: the slave population." *Journal of Roman Studies* 95: 64-79.
- Scheidel, Walter. 2006. "The demography of Roman state formation in Italy." In Martin Jehne and Rene Pfeilschifter, eds., *Herrschaft ohne Integration? Rom und Italien in republikanischer Zeit*. Frankfurt: Verlag Antike: 207-226.
- Scheidel, Walter. 2008. "The comparative economics of slavery in the Greco-Roman world." In Enrico Dal Lago and Constantina Katsari, eds., *Slave systems, ancient and modern*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 105-126.
- Scheidel, Walter. 2011. "The Roman slave supply." In Bradley and Cartledge, eds. 2011: 287-310.
- Scheidel, Walter. 2012. "Slavery." In Walter Scheidel, ed., *The Cambridge companion to the Roman economy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 89-113.
- Scheidel, Walter 2018. "Comparing comparisons." In Geoffrey E. Lloyd and Jingyi J. Zhao, eds. *Ancient Greece and China compared: interdisciplinary and cross-cultural perspectives*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 40-58.
- Smaldone, Joseph P. 1977. *Warfare in the Sokoto caliphate: historical and sociological perspectives*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Stan, Marius G. 2014. "The phenomenon of Roman republican coinage in pre-Roman Dacia: a reexamination of the evidence." *Journal of Ancient History and Archaeology* 1.4: 44-67.

- Stilwell, Sean. 2000. "Power, honour and shame: the ideology of royal slavery in the Sokoto caliphate." *Africa* 70: 394-421.
- Taylor, Timothy. 2001. "Believing the ancients: quantitative and qualitative dimensions of slavery and the slave trade in later prehistoric Europe." *World Archaeology* 33: 27-43.
- Terrenato, Nicola. 2019. *The early Roman expansion into Italy: elite negotiation and family agendas*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Vlassopoulos, Kostas. 2016. "Finley's slavery." In Daniel Jew, Robin Osborne and Michael Scott, eds., *M. I. Finley: an ancient historian and his impact*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 76-99.
- Volkman, Hans. 1990. *Die Massenversklavungen der Einwohner erobelter Städte in der hellenistisch-römischen Zeit*. 2nd ed. by Gerhard Horsmann. Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag.
- Welwei, Karl-Wilhelm. 2000. *Sub corona vendere: Quellenkritische Studien zu Kriegsgefangenschaft und Sklaverei in Rom bis zum Ende des Hannibalskrieges*. Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag.
- Wilson, Andrew. 2012. "Saharan trade in the Roman period: short-, medium- and long-distance trade networks." *Azania* 47: 409-449.
- Zeuske, Michael. 2013. *Handbuch der Geschichte der Sklaverei: eine Globalgeschichte von den Anfängen bis zur Gegenwart*. Berlin: De Gruyter.